

On Energy Harvesting of Hybrid TDMA-NOMA Systems

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Abstract—In this paper, we investigate energy harvesting capabilities of non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) scheme integrated with the conventional time division multiple access (TDMA) scheme, which is referred to as hybrid TDMA-NOMA system. In a such hybrid scheme, users are divided into a number of groups, with the total time allocated for transmission is shared between these groups through multiple time slots. In particular, a time slot is assigned to serve each group, whereas the users in the corresponding group are served based on power-domain NOMA technique. Furthermore, simultaneous wireless power and information transfer technique is utilized to simultaneously harvest energy and decode information at each user. Therefore, each user splits the received signal into two parts, namely, energy harvesting part and information decoding part. In particular, we jointly determine the power allocation and power splitting ratios for all users to minimize the transmit power under minimum rate and minimum energy harvesting requirements at each user. Furthermore, this joint design is a non-convex problem in nature. Hence, we employ successive interference cancellation to overcome these non-convexity issues and determine the design parameters (i.e., the power allocations and the power splitting ratios). In simulation results, we demonstrate the performance of the proposed hybrid TDMA-NOMA design and show that it outperforms the conventional TDMA scheme in terms of transmit power consumption.

Index Terms—Non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA), energy harvesting, time division multiple access (TDMA), hybrid TDMA-NOMA, simultaneous wireless power and information transfer (SWIPT).

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) has been envisioned as a promising multiple access candidate towards the fifth generation (5G) and beyond wireless networks [1]. In contrast to the conventional orthogonal multiple access (OMA) schemes; namely time division multiple access (TDMA) and orthogonal frequency division multiple access (OFDMA), NOMA has the potential to serve multiple users simultaneously within the same resource block (RB) [2] [3]. In particular, this can be accomplished by employing superposition coding at the base station (BS) [4], such that the messages intended to different users are encoded with different power levels. Furthermore, successive interference cancellation (SIC) is exploited at receiver ends for multiuser detection [5] [4] [6]. Considering the fact that NOMA can serve multiple users simultaneously in the same RB, NOMA

is expected to play a crucial role to support the proliferation of Internet-of-Things (IoT) in future wireless networks [7]. However, the error propagation introduced in the SIC process might impose some constraints on the practical implementation of NOMA especially in dense networks [8]. To mitigate this error propagation issue and to facilitate practical implementation of NOMA in dense network, NOMA can be incorporated with different key technologies to meet various system requirements [9]. For example, NOMA is integrated with spatial domain multiple access (SDMA); in such a hybrid SDMA-NOMA approach [10], multiple users can be grouped in a cluster and served based on NOMA, while a spatial beam is assigned to establish communication with each cluster. Furthermore, NOMA can be applied with the existing conventional OMA schemes, including hybrid TDMA-NOMA and hybrid OFDMA-NOMA [8]. In such hybrid schemes, an orthogonal RB (i.e., time slot or frequency slot) is assigned to serve a group of users, whereas the users in each group are served based on NOMA. These hybrid systems can offer different advantages over the conventional systems. Firstly, the integration of NOMA with the SDMA/OMA schemes provides additional degrees of freedom which can be exploited with the available domains [8], [10]. Secondly, it is obvious that users' grouping (i.e., clustering) minimizes the effects of inevitable errors associated with SIC by significantly reducing the required number of SIC implementations [11].

However, massive connectivity offered by these hybrid schemes has a direct negative impact on the power consumption of these systems. As a result, an explosive growth in the power consumption is inevitable [12], which brings up different environmental issues including global warming and natural disasters, as well as financial pressures on both service providers and consumers [12]. To address these issues, the power consumption in wireless transmission is mainly considered by either allocating the power resources to maximize the energy efficiency of the systems [12] [13] [14], or by incorporating the novel simultaneous wireless power and information transfer (SWIPT) technique [15]. In SWIPT, the receiver has the capability to simultaneously harvest

energy and decode information [15]. In particular, this could be accomplished by splitting the received radio frequency (RF) signal through either time splitting or power splitting techniques [16]. Despite of the low complexity of the former, this requires a better synchronization between the receiver and the transmitter to precisely perform the splitting [15], and thus, the latter is typically more desirable. In fact, SWIPT is expected to contribute in feeding the power-hungry users, especially in ultra-dense sensor networks, where hundreds of unreachable sensors seek power to extend their life-time [15]. In particular, the co-channel interference introduced by exploiting the same RB to serve multiple users in the hybrid TDMA-NOMA has the potential to improve the energy harvesting (EH) capability compared to the conventional TDMA systems.

In this paper, we investigate the EH capabilities of the multi-user single-input single-output (SISO) hybrid TDMA-NOMA system. In particular, we first introduce the hybrid TDMA-NOMA system model considering the EH capability of each user. Then, we evaluate the required minimum transmit power at BS to meet the quality-of-service (QoS) requirements. In fact, these requirements include the minimum rate and minimum harvested power at each user. The design parameters, i.e., the power allocations and the power splitting ratios, corresponding to the minimum transmit power are jointly determined through solving a power minimization (P-Min) problem for the hybrid TDMA-NOMA scheme. However, due to the non-convexity of the P-Min problem, sequential convex approximation (SCA) is exploited to *jointly* optimize these design parameters. Finally, we compare the performance of the proposed hybrid NOMA-TDMA design with that of the conventional TDMA scheme.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the system model and the problem formulation. Section III presents the proposed technique to solve the formulated optimization problem, with additional discussions on the TDMA-NOMA system. Section IV provides simulation results which evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed joint design by comparing its performance with that of the conventional TDMA scheme. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

A. System Model

We consider a multi-user SISO hybrid TDMA-NOMA system with K users, where the k^{th} single-antenna user (u_k) is located at a distance d_k (in meter) from the BS. Furthermore, the users are divided into C groups, and the available time for transmission (T) is divided equally among these groups, as shown in Fig. 1. The number of users in the i^{th} group (G_i) is denoted by K_i , $\forall i \in \mathcal{C} \triangleq \{1, 2, \dots, C\}$, such that $K = \sum_{i=1}^C K_i$. Note that the time slot allocated to serve group G_i is denoted by t_i , such that $T = \sum_{i=1}^C t_i$, and $t_i = \frac{T}{C}$. Furthermore, the j^{th} user in G_i is denoted by $u_{j,i}$. In particular, user grouping has a considerable impact on the

performance of the hybrid TDMA-NOMA system. Hence, we discuss the user grouping strategies in the next section.

Fig. 1: Hybrid TDMA-NOMA system; the users are divided among C groups.

Furthermore, multiple users in each group are served based on NOMA, such that the transmit signal at the BS at t_i is denoted by x_i , expressed as

$$x_i = \sum_{j=1}^{K_i} p_{j,i} x_{j,i}. \quad (1)$$

Note that $p_{j,i}^2$ and $x_{j,i}$ denote the allocated power and the signal intended to the j^{th} user in G_i (i.e., $u_{j,i}$), respectively. Based on this, the received signal at $u_{j,i}$ can be expressed as

$$r_{j,i} = h_{j,i} x_i + n_{j,i}, \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i \triangleq \{1, 2, \dots, K_i\}, \quad (2)$$

where $h_{j,i}$ is the channel coefficient between the BS and $u_{j,i}$. In particular, the corresponding channel gain can be written as $|h_{j,i}|^2 = \frac{\eta}{(d_{j,i}/d_o)^\kappa}$ [17], where d_o and $d_{j,i}$ represent the reference distance and the distance between $u_{j,i}$ and the BS (in meters), respectively. Furthermore, η and κ represent the signal attenuation at d_o and the path loss exponent, respectively. In addition, $n_{j,i}$ is the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance $\sigma_{j,i}^2$ dBm/Hz. In fact, user ordering at each group plays a crucial role on the performance of NOMA systems [18]. Note that the optimal ordering can be determined through an exhaustive search among all ordering possibilities, which is not possible in practical scenarios, especially in dense networks [19], [20]. Hence, we order the users in each group based on their channel strengths [21], [14], as follows:

$$|h_{1,i}|^2 \geq |h_{2,i}|^2 \geq \dots \geq |h_{K_i,i}|^2, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}. \quad (3)$$

Now, we assume that each user has a potential capability to split the received signal into two parts such that $\sqrt{\beta_{j,i}}$ (i.e., $0 < \beta_{j,i} < 1$) of $r_{j,i}$ is used to decode information, whereas $\sqrt{1 - \beta_{j,i}}$ of $r_{j,i}$ is utilized to harvest energy, as shown in Fig. 2.

Information Decoding (ID) Stage: At this stage, the fraction of received signal $\sqrt{\beta_{j,i}}$ of $r_{j,i}$ is utilized to decode the information. Therefore, the signal split to the ID stage

Fig. 2: Illustration of splitting the received signal at $u_{j,i}$.

can be written as follows:

$$\tilde{r}_{j,i} = \sqrt{\beta_{j,i}} \left(h_{j,i} \sum_{s=1}^{K_i} p_{s,i} x_{s,i} + n_{j,i} \right) + \tilde{n}_{j,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \quad (4)$$

where $\tilde{n}_{j,i}$ is AWGN with zero mean and variance $\tilde{\sigma}_{j,i}^2$ dBm/Hz, which is introduced due to processing $r_{j,i}$ on the ID stage [22], [15], [23]. Based on the user ordering defined in (3), $u_{j,i}$ performs SIC to detect and remove the signals of the weaker users $u_{j+1,i} \cdots u_{K_i,i}$ prior to decoding its own signal. Note that we assume that SIC is implemented with no errors. Hence, the received signal at $u_{j,i}$ after employing SIC can be written as follows:

$$\tilde{r}_{j,i}^{\text{SIC}} = \sqrt{\beta_{j,i}} \left(h_{j,i} p_{j,i} x_{j,i} + h_{j,i} \sum_{s=1}^{j-1} p_{s,i} x_{s,i} + n_{j,i} \right) + \tilde{n}_{j,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i. \quad (5)$$

Accordingly, the signal-to-interference and noise ratio (SINR) at which $u_{j,i}$ decodes the message of $u_{d,i} \forall d \in \{j+1, \dots, K_i\}$ can be written as

$$\text{SINR}_{j,i}^d = \frac{\beta_{j,i} |h_{j,i}|^2 p_{d,i}^2}{\beta_{j,i} |h_{j,i}|^2 \sum_{s=1}^{d-1} p_{s,i}^2 + \beta_{j,i} \sigma_{j,i}^2 + \tilde{\sigma}_{j,i}^2}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall d \in \{j+1, j+2, \dots, K_i\}. \quad (6)$$

Note that $u_{j,i}$ has the capability to decode the message of the weaker user $u_{d,i} \forall d \in \{j+1, \dots, K_i\}$ if and only if the messages intended to these weaker users are received at $u_{j,i}$ with higher SINR compared to that of the users with stronger channel conditions. In particular, this can be guaranteed by including the following condition:

$$p_{K_i,i}^2 \geq p_{K_i-1,i}^2 \geq \dots \geq p_{1,i}^2, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}. \quad (7)$$

The above constraint is referred to as SIC constraint throughout this paper. Based on this condition, the SINR of $u_{j,i}$ can be defined as [24]

$$\text{SINR}_{j,i} = \min\{\text{SINR}_{j,i}^1, \text{SINR}_{j,i}^2, \dots, \text{SINR}_{j,i}^j\}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i. \quad (8)$$

Therefore, the achieved rate at $u_{j,i}$ can be written as follows:

$$R_{j,i} = t_i \log_2(1 + \text{SINR}_{j,i}), \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i. \quad (9)$$

Note that the total required transmit power at the BS can be expressed as $P_t = \sum_{i=1}^C \sum_{j=1}^{K_i} p_{j,i}^2$.

EH Stage: Next, we consider the received signal part at the EH stage. In particular, the EH circuit consists of a matching network, a radio frequency to direct current (RF-DC) converter, and a storage unit [25] [26]. The signal split to the EH stage can be written as

$$\hat{r}_{j,i} = \sqrt{(1 - \beta_{j,i})} \left(h_{j,i} \sum_{s=1}^{K_i} p_{s,i} x_{s,i} + n_{j,i} \right) + \hat{n}_{j,i}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \quad (10)$$

where $\hat{n}_{j,i}$ is AWGN introduced by the processing of the received signal at the EH stage with zero mean and variance $\hat{\sigma}_{j,i}^2$ dBm/Hz. Note that $\hat{r}_{j,i}$ is utilized to harvest the energy at $u_{j,i}$. Hence, the harvested power at $u_{j,i}$ can be defined as [16]

$$P_{j,i} = \eta (1 - \beta_{j,i}) \left(|h_{j,i}|^2 \sum_{s=1}^{K_i} p_{s,i}^2 \right), \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \quad (11)$$

where $\eta \in [0, 1]$ is the efficiency of the RF-DC in the EH stage [26]. Note that the total harvested power by all users in the system (P_H) can be written as $P_H = \sum_{i=1}^C \sum_{j=1}^{K_i} P_{j,i}$.

B. Problem Formulation

In this subsection, we formulate a problem to investigate the EH capabilities of the hybrid TDMA-NOMA scheme through a power minimization (i.e., P-Min) design. In particular, the BS aims to minimize the transmit power (i.e., P_t) under minimum harvesting power and minimum data rate requirements at each user. Note that this design seeks to determine a power allocation (i.e., $p_{j,i}$) and a power splitting ratio (i.e., $\beta_{j,i}$) $\forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i$ for each user in the system. These design parameters can be determined through solving the following P-Min problem:

$$OP_P: \text{minimize}_{\{p_{j,i}, \beta_{j,i}\}_{i=1}^C} \sum_{i=1}^C \sum_{j=1}^{K_i} p_{j,i}^2 \quad (12a)$$

$$\text{subject to } R_{j,i} \geq R^{\min}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \quad (12b)$$

$$P_{j,i} \geq P^{\min}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \quad (12c)$$

$$p_{K_i,i}^2 \geq \dots \geq p_{1,i}^2, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \quad (12d)$$

$$0 \leq \beta_{j,i} \leq 1, \quad \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall i \in \mathcal{C}. \quad (12e)$$

Note that R^{\min} and P^{\min} denote the minimum rate and minimum harvested power requirements at each user, respectively. It is obvious that the optimization problem in (12) is non-convex due to the non-convex constraints in (12b) and (12c). Furthermore, the solution of this optimization problem needs to be determined by jointly optimizing the design parameters $\{p_{j,i}, \beta_{j,i}\} \forall i, \forall j$.

III. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we propose an iterative approach to jointly solve the original non-convex optimization problem in (12). Later in this section, we shed some light on the initial

parameters selection and convergence of the proposed iterative approach. We first provide a brief discussion on the proposed grouping strategy in the following subsection.

A. Grouping Strategy

Choosing an appropriate grouping strategy plays a crucial role on the performance of the hybrid TDMA-NOMA system, as the optimal solution of OP_P can be only determined by formulating the best groups [27]. In particular, the optimal required transmit power can be only determined by solving OP_P with an exhaustive search among all possible set of groups [28]. However, it is expensive in terms of computational complexity and unaffordable in practical systems, including IoTs in future wireless networks. Furthermore, the difference between the channel strengths of the users in the same group is another key factor that determines the overall performance of the system. As the users within each group are served based on NOMA, the practical implementation of the SIC technique requires the difference between the channel strengths of the users to be as large as possible [8]. Furthermore, grouping users with a similar channel strength would introduce errors in the SIC implementation, which would degrade the overall performance of the system [29]. Based on this key fact, we group the users such that the difference between their channel strengths is as high as possible. For example, with two users in each group (i.e., $K_i = 2$), the user groups based on the proposed grouping strategy can be defined as

$$\left(\{u_{1,1}, u_{2,1}\}, \{u_{1,2}, u_{2,2}\}, \dots, \{u_{1,C}, u_{2,C}\} \right) \equiv \left(\{u_1, u_K\}, \{u_2, u_{K-1}\}, \dots, \{u_{\frac{K}{2}}, u_{\frac{K}{2}+1}\} \right). \quad (13a)$$

B. Proposed Algorithm

With the assumption that the users have been already grouped into groups as in (13a), we now solve the non-convex optimization problem OP_P through the SCA technique. In SCA, the non-convex terms are approximated by a set of lower bounded convex terms, and then, the original non-convex problem is solved with these approximated convex problem. Note that SCA has been utilized to solve different non-convex optimization problem in the literature [19], [20], [14]. We start handling the non-convexity of the constraint in (12b) by introducing new slack variables $\vartheta_{j,i}$ and $\theta_{j,i}$, such that,

$$R_{j,i} \geq \vartheta_{j,i}, \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i. \quad (14a)$$

$$(1 + \text{SINR}_{j,i}^d) \geq \theta_{j,i}, \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall d \in \{j+1, \dots, \mathcal{K}_i\}, \quad (14b)$$

$$\theta_{j,i} \geq 2^{\vartheta_{j,i}}, \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i. \quad (14c)$$

To handle the non-convexity of (14b), we first insert a slack variable $\chi_{j,i}$ such that

$$\frac{\beta_{j,i}|h_{j,i}|^2 p_{d,i}^2}{\beta_{j,i}|h_{j,i}|^2 \sum_{s=1}^{d-1} p_{s,i}^2 + \beta_{j,i} \sigma_{j,i}^2 + \tilde{\sigma}_{j,i}^2} \geq \frac{(\theta_{j,i} - 1) \chi_{j,i}^2}{\chi_{j,i}^2}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall d \in \{j+1, j+2, \dots, \mathcal{K}_i\}. \quad (15)$$

Then, we decompose the constraint in (15) into the following two constraints:

$$\beta_{j,i}|h_{j,i}|^2 p_{d,i}^2 \geq (\theta_{j,i} - 1) \chi_{j,i}^2, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall d \in \{j+1, j+2, \dots, \mathcal{K}_i\}, \quad (16)$$

$$\beta_{j,i}|h_{j,i}|^2 \sum_{s=1}^{d-1} p_{s,i}^2 + \beta_{j,i} \sigma_{j,i}^2 + \tilde{\sigma}_{j,i}^2 \leq \chi_{j,i}^2, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall d \in \{j+1, j+2, \dots, \mathcal{K}_i\}. \quad (17)$$

To handle the non-convexity of these constraints, we insert another slack variable $\alpha_{j,i}^d$ such that

$$\beta_{j,i} p_{d,i}^2 \geq \alpha_{j,i}^d, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall d \in \{j+1, j+2, \dots, \mathcal{K}_i\}. \quad (18)$$

It is obvious that the constraint in (18) is still non-convex. Therefore, we exploit the first-order Taylor series to approximate the left-hand side of (18) with a linear term. Doing so, the approximated convex form of (18) can be written as

$$\beta_{j,i}^{(t)} p_{d,i}^{2(t)} + 2p_{d,i}^{(t)} \beta_{j,i}^{(t)} (p_{d,i} - p_{d,i}^{(t)}) + p_{d,i}^{2(t)} (\beta_{j,i} - \beta_{j,i}^{(t)}) \geq \alpha_{j,i}^d, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall d \in \{j+1, j+2, \dots, \mathcal{K}_i\}, \quad (19)$$

where $\beta_{j,i}^{(t)}$ and $p_{d,i}^{(t)}$ represent the approximations of $\beta_{j,i}$ and $p_{d,i}$ at the t^{th} iteration, respectively. By incorporating these slack variables, the non-convex constraint in (16) can be approximately replaced by the following convex constraint:

$$|h_{j,i}|^2 \alpha_{j,i}^d \geq \chi_{j,i}^{2(t)} (\theta_{j,i}^{(t)} - 1) + 2 (\theta_{j,i}^{(t)} - 1) \chi_{j,i}^{(t)} (\chi_{j,i} - \chi_{j,i}^{(t)}) + \chi_{j,i}^{2(t)} (\theta_{j,i} - \theta_{j,i}^{(t)}), \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall d \in \{j+1, j+2, \dots, \mathcal{K}_i\}. \quad (20)$$

Note that the non-convex right-hand side of inequality (16) is approximated with a linear term. Similarly, the approximated convex form of constraint (17) is written as

$$\chi_{j,i}^{2(t)} + 2\chi_{j,i}^{(t)} (\chi_{j,i} - \chi_{j,i}^{(t)}) \geq \gamma \left(|h_{j,i}|^2 \sum_{s=1}^{d-1} \alpha_{j,i}^s + \sigma_{j,i}^2 \beta_{j,i} + \tilde{\sigma}_{j,i}^2 \right). \quad (21a)$$

Based on these multiple slack variables, the achieved rate at each user (i.e., $R_{j,i}$) can be equivalently approximated by $\vartheta_{j,i}$ with the constraints in (14c), (19), (20), and (21).

Next, we tackle the non-convexity of the constraint in (12c) by incorporating slack variables $\rho_{i,j}$ and $\varrho_{i,j}$, such that

$$(1 - \beta_{j,i}) p_{s,i}^2 \geq \rho_{j,i}^s, \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall s \in \mathcal{K}_i, \quad (22a)$$

$$\eta |h_{j,i}|^2 \sum_{s=1}^{K_i} \rho_{j,i}^s \geq \varrho_{i,j}, \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i. \quad (22b)$$

Without loss of generality, the non-convex constraint in (22a) can be tackled by following the same approximations devel-

oped to handle the previous constraint in (18). Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} & (1 - \beta_{j,i}^{(t)}) p_{s,i}^{2,(t)} + 2p_{s,i}^{(t)} (1 - \beta_{j,i}^{(t)}) (p_{s,i} - p_{s,i}^{(t)}) \\ & - p_{s,i}^{2,(t)} (\beta_{j,i} - \beta_{j,i}^{(t)}) \geq \rho_{j,i}^s, \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \forall s \in \mathcal{K}_i. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Finally, the non-convexity of the SIC constraint in (12d) is tackled by replacing each element in this constraint by the following linear approximation:

$$p_{K_i,i}^2 \geq p_{K_i,i}^{2,(t)} + 2p_{K_i,i}^{(t)} (p_{K_i,i} - p_{K_i,i}^{(t)}), \forall i. \quad (24)$$

Based on these multiple slack variable incorporations, the non-convex optimization problem in (12) can be equivalently written as

$$OP_1: \underset{\Gamma}{\text{minimize}} \quad \sum_{i=1}^C \sum_{j=1}^{K_i} p_{j,i}^2 \quad (25a)$$

$$\text{subject to } r_{j,i} \geq R^{\min}, \varrho_{j,i} \geq P^{\min}, \forall i \in \mathcal{C}, \forall j \in \mathcal{K}_i, \quad (25b)$$

$$(12d), (12e), (14c), (19), (20), (21), (23), \quad (25c)$$

where Γ includes all the optimization variables involved in the P-Min design: $\Gamma = \{p_{j,i}, r_{j,i}, \beta_{j,i}, \varrho_{j,i}, \rho_{j,i}, \alpha_{j,i}\}_{i=1}^K$. The solution of the optimization problem in (25) requires an appropriate selection of the initial variables (i.e., $\Gamma^{(0)}$). Therefore, random initial power allocations $\{p_{j,i}^{(0)}\}_{i=1}^K$ are assumed. Then, the corresponding initial power splitting ratios (i.e., $\{\beta_{j,i}^{(0)}\}_{i=1}^K$) that satisfy the constraints of the original optimization problem OP_P , are evaluated. Furthermore, the remaining slack variables $\rho_{j,i}^{(0)}$ and $\alpha_{j,i}^{(0)}$ can be determined by substituting $\{p_{j,i}^{(0)}\}_{i=1}^K$ and $\{\beta_{j,i}^{(0)}\}_{i=1}^K$ in (19) and (20), respectively. The algorithm proposed to solve the original P-Min problem is summarized in Algorithm 1. The algorithm terminates when the absolute difference between two sequential optimal values is less than a defined threshold μ .

Algorithm 1: P-Min Design using SCA.

- Step 1: Group users based on (13a)
Step 2: Initialize all design parameters $\Gamma^{(0)}$
Step 3: Repeat
 1) Solve the optimization problem in (25)
 2) Update $\Gamma^{(n+1)}$
Step 4: Until required accuracy is achieved.
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To demonstrate the performance of the proposed EH design of the hybrid TDMA-NOMA system, we evaluate and compare its performance with that of the conventional TDMA system. In the TDMA system, each time slot ($t_i^{\text{TDMA}} = \frac{T}{K}$) is employed to serve only one user. Based on this time slot assignment, the achieved rate at u_i can be written as

$$R_i^{\text{TDMA}} = t_i^{\text{TDMA}} \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{\beta_i |h_i|^2 p_i^2}{\beta_i \sigma_i^2 + \bar{\sigma}_i^2} \right), \forall i \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (26)$$

On the other hand, the harvested power at u_i in this conventional TDMA can be represented as

$$P_i^{\text{TDMA}} = \eta(1 - \beta_i) |h_i|^2 p_i^2, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (27)$$

Now, we formulate a similar P-Min problem in a TDMA system with minimum rate and minimum energy harvesting constraints. As such,

$$OP_2: \underset{\{p_i, \beta_i\}_{i=1}^K}{\text{minimize}} \quad \sum_{i=1}^K p_i^2 \quad (28a)$$

$$\text{subject to } R_i^{\text{TDMA}} \geq R^{\min}, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}, \quad (28b)$$

$$P_i^{\text{TDMA}} \geq P^{\min}, \forall i \in \mathcal{K}. \quad (28c)$$

Note that the developed optimization problem in (28) for the TDMA system is solved using the same SCA technique.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we demonstrate the EH capability of the proposed hybrid TDMA-NOMA scheme by evaluating and comparing its performance with that of the conventional TDMA scheme. In these numerical simulations, we consider ten users (i.e., $K = 10$) that are uniformly distributed in a circle of radius 10 meter from the BS. In addition, these users are divided into five groups (i.e., $C = 5$). Table I summarizes the different parameters adopted in simulations [17]. Note that all simulation results are averaged over 500 channel realizations. In addition, the CVX toolbox is used to generate results in this section. Fig. 3 illustrates

TABLE I: Parameter values used in simulations.

Parameter	Value
Number of users (K)	10
Number of groups (C)	5
Number of users in each group (K_i)	2
Path loss exponent (κ)	2
Reference distance (d_0)	1
Signal attenuation at d_0 (η)	-30 dB
$\sigma_i^2, \bar{\sigma}_{j,i}^2, \bar{\sigma}_{j,i}^2$ (dBm/Hz)	-100
Efficiency of converter (η)	0.75

and compares the minimum required transmit power (i.e., P_t) against a range of minimum harvest power requirements P^{\min} for the hybrid TDMA-NOMA and the conventional TDMA systems. As expected, P_t of both systems increases with the increase of P^{\min} . Furthermore, as shown in Fig. 3, the hybrid TDMA-NOMA scheme exhibits a better performance, as it consumes less P_t compared to the conventional TDMA system. In particular, users grouping in the hybrid TDMA-NOMA system introduces higher interference levels, which facilitates the satisfaction of the minimum harvested power requirements with lower P_t compared to the conventional TDMA system. Next, we evaluate the number of iterations required for the convergence of SCA algorithm to solve OP_P for two different minimum harvested power requirements. As seen in Fig. 4, the algorithm converges to the solution within a few number of iterations.

Fig. 3: The required transmit power versus different minimum harvest power requirements P^{\min} , with a minimum rate requirement $R^{\min} = 10^{-1}$ bit/Hz.

Fig. 4: The convergence of the SCA algorithm to solve OP_P for different values of the minimum harvest power requirement P^{\min} , $R^{\min} = 10^{-2}$ bit/Hz.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we investigated the energy harvesting capabilities of a multi-user SISO hybrid TDMA-NOMA system. In such a hybrid system, users are divided into a number of groups, with a time slot assigned to serve each group and NOMA employed to serve users within a group. For the proposed scheme, we evaluated the required minimum power to meet the minimum rate and minimum harvest energy requirements at each user. Simulation results confirmed that the proposed hybrid TDMA-NOMA system outperforms the conventional TDMA system in terms of the minimum required transmit power.

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